

1 **Ep300 activation defines a common epigenetic route in chronic disease.**

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7 We measured total transcription in cells and tissues from patients with chronic disease either of
8 autoimmune or CNS neurodegenerative nature. We observed recurrent activation of Ep300 in humans
9 with chronic disease including in the blood in humans with Crohn's Disease and in an iPS stem cell model
10 of Alzheimer's Disease. In humans with CD, Ep300 activation seemed modular and was highest during
11 established but inactive disease, diminishing in significance during periods of active disease.

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Citations

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